

MOTOR ALALIYA- COMPLEX SPEECH DEFECT CHANGES

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A little-studied part of speech disorders - systemic speech disorder - called alalia is one of the problems that requires deep study today. According to the Russian defektologist-scientist Kovshikov, speech impairment occurs in 0.1% of the population. In addition, this indicator changes depending on age. Pre-school children suffering from alalia make up 1.0%. Among children of school age - 0, 6%, middle and older children - 0, 2%. Speech pathology in different age groups makes up 0.5% of speech pathology, and approximately 4.0% in children. Alalia is more common in boy; The prevalence ratio between boys and girls is 2:1.

Many children with alalia do not master speech and do not speak even by the time they enter school.

A complex symptom of linguistic and non-linguistic disorders like alalia, it can negatively impact language, cognitive development and aspects of personality, including interference with needs and aspirations that are often critical to personality development..

The stages in the history of studying the problem of speech disorders of alalia can be distinguished as follows:

- 1) from 1875 to the 60s of the twentieth century;
- 2) From the 1960s to the present.

One stage - the known surface properties of the object are taken for its significance. However, the internal properties of the object and their behavior are not taken into account. The reasons for the failure of the language mechanism were related to the failure of fine motor skills or various intellectual processes.

The second stage is the internal structure of the language process in which the linguistic and psycholinguistic aspects prevail and its determination;

Alalia was first identified in 1875 by F. Clarus. Among the cases of aphasia in children, it is one of the most common cases of "congenital aphasia".

In 1877, A. Kussmaul described one case of speech deficiency in children, who seemed to have all the necessary conditions to acquire it, and this defect was called congenital aphasia.

In 1885-1886, I. A. Baudouin and Courtenay gave a clear linguistic description of the condition of congenital aphasia. In the scientist's opinion, "congenital aphasia" shows us the pathological type of language acquisition, the failure to master the rules of its operation.

In 1888, R. Cohen for the first time offered a comprehensive picture of "idiopathic alalia" (hearing deficiency), concluding on its etiology, the nature, mechanism, dynamics, symptoms, differential diagnosis and methods of training speech in these children.

R. Luchzinger in 1970, M. Berry in 1957, M. B. Eidinova in 1961, and V. A. Kovshikov in 1985 emphasized that brain injury and asphyxia of newborns play a leading role in the benefit of the disease. among others, they spoke in alalia; described the linguistic and psychological appearance of underdevelopment.

In modern practice, synonymous terms denoting systemic underdevelopment of speech are found: alalia, developmental aphasia, ontogenetic aphasia.

Alalia (according to G. V. Chirkina) is the absence of speech or its systematic underdevelopment in children with normal hearing and a perfectly preserved intellect.

Alalia (according to B.M. Grinspun) is the absence or underdevelopment of speech due to organic damage to the speech zones of the cerebral cortex in the perinatal or early period of child development.

Alaliya (according to M. E. Khvattsev) is the development of intellectual abilities, hearing and speech organs for the development of speech.

The main reasons for language underdevelopment in children are represented by the following:

- biological - disorders in the structure of the brain hemisphere caused by a decrease in the functionality of the two hemispheres of the brain, various injuries of the central nervous system;
- unfavorable conditions for social development and education.

Together with this, the difference in the dominance of the left hemisphere of speech is determined by a significant decrease in the functional capabilities of the right hemisphere, which is not dominant in speaking.

Biological causes are studied in three periods:

Perinatal period: Intoxication; diseases of mothers to be adjusted; fetus circulatory failure mother's fall and injury; damage to the fetus later; risk of abortion, parental hereditary diseases, pregnancy infection in the womb.

Natal period: long-term birth; fast birth; asphyxia of the newborn branch, various failures of birth control by the obstetric service, anesthesia.

Postnatal period: early childhood head injury, infectious hepatitis, meningitis; frequent somatic diseases, diseases to be adjusted; frequent infectious diseases, disability.

Social reasons: the mother's exhaustion or short-term deprivation, disagreements in the family, lack of or incorrect interaction with the child, parents' lack of understanding of the developmental features of children with pathologies of the central nervous system, and speech pathologies in the family.

In the clinical-pedagogical classification, alalia refers to the failure of the structural-semantic (internal) structure, systematic, polymorphous speaking disorders. При алалии нарушается общение, нарушается язык общения, то есть нарушается особая автономная знаковая система. У детей с алалией изначально имеется речевая патология..

Alalia as a nosological unit is classified by a malfunction of the sub-systems of language existence:

- phonetic,
- phonemics
- syntax,
- morphological
- semantics,
- lexical,

The level of speech disorders in children can be different and manifest themselves on the border from a complete (or almost complete) absence of expressive speech to minor disturbances in the functioning of speech subsystems:

- easy,
- average heavy,
- heavy.

This classification is based on criteria that take into account the location of the brain injury. Based on this feature, the following types of alalia are distinguished:

- motoring,
- sensory,
- sensorimotor,
- optics.

Motor alalia occurs due to disorders of the central speech-motor analyzer. The child begins to understand other people's speech at their own time, but their own speech is not developed.

R. A. Belova-David, while studying children with motor paralysis, determined motor afferent and motor efferent paralysis, depending on which part of the speech movement analyzer was affected.

Afferent motor alalia occurs due to the pathology of the postcentral zone of the cerebral hemisphere (the left hemisphere's left hemisphere), which is usually responsible for the kinesthetic analysis and synthesis of stimuli, sensations entering the brain during speech, and kinesthetic speech programs. If this zone is damaged, kinesthetic articular apraxia (or its elements) may appear. In this case, the child has difficulty finding individual articulations, his speech is characterized by alternating sounds with articulatory conflict. For example, the child cannot say or repeat a word or phrase. It is difficult to establish correct articulation in speech.

Efferent motor alalia occurs due to the pathology of the premotor zone of the cerebral cortex (inferior parietal branch of the left hemisphere - Broca's center), which is usually responsible for the sequence and organization of complex sets of movement programs. Kinetic articular apraxia (or its elements) can be observed in efferent motor paralysis. In this case, the child has difficulty moving from one co-articulation to another, the child has difficulty introducing movements and performing single-line movements. In children's speech, the speech structure of the words is grossly defective (along with it, the voice accentuation goes into the background), and perseverations (pathological involuntary repetition of common elements of speech) can be observed.

Alalia is a complex defect of speech, different in terms of mechanisms, appearance, and level of underdevelopment of speech (tongue). Based on the chosen approach to its study and the observed differences in the appearance of the disease, researchers have identified several types of this disease.

Depending on the presence of neuropsychiatric diseases, Alalia is divided into the following:

- not affected by these diseases (health);
- heavy (combined).

The following questions remain competitive in the classification of Alalia:

- establishment of causal relationships between speaking and non-speaking processes;
- to explain alalia as an unbiased nosological unit entering the mass of language diseases that are not causally related to the conditions of the sensory or motor components of speech processes, including mental conditions.

According to the clinical classification, M. Zeeman divides intermediate speech defects (dysphasia) in childhood into motor aphasia, agraphia, alexia, receptive dysphatic diseases with typical symptoms of dysphatic diseases with preserved understanding, and in the second case, sensory aphasia.

According to the opinion of one line of experts (K. P. Becker, M. Sovak, M. Critchley, etc.), the central speech defects in alalia are oral acoustic agnosia (inability to accept oral signs) and oral motor apraxia (oral signs, lack of ability to create and repeat patterns)

Let's make it clear that the object of children's speech therapy is the ontogenesis of real speech in the normal state of hearing, vision and intellect, the failure of children's speech due to defective, underdeveloped psychological or physiological mechanisms or injury in the initial stages.

These defects belong to the undeveloped stage of primary speech. Modern classifications of speech defects are focused primarily on primary defects.

Speech disorders in children and adolescents manifest themselves in different aspects:

- Etiopathogenesis - the organic and functional causes of the defect and characteristic symptom complexes determining the forms of speech defects were determined;
- the relationship between speech and thinking;
- to distinguish speech failure and speech disorders in sensory (emotional) disorders.

Differential diagnosis of alalia is a complex problem because today the definition of the full symptom complex of alalia syndrome remains relevant.

At all stages of the development of an alalic child, the automation of the speaking process occurs, and the dynamic stereotype of the speaking activity is not developed, which leads to the formation of a special pathological type of linguistic activity.

The only faulty link in the structure of the motor system is the lack of formation of the activity.

A secondary link in the structure of the motor defect is a failure of the communicative function of speech and behavior, which is often seen and is accompanied by behavioral negativity.

Children with motor alalia are characterized by very low speech activity. Accordingly, the higher the child's hearing and the more critical relationship in his speech, the more clearly his secondary compensatory forms of interaction with others using facial expressions and gestures appeared. In the heavy form of motor learning, he can extract only one sentence from the most frequently used sentences, and he cannot learn the elements of the grammatical field of the word without special education.

There are frequent pauses and stops in the speech of a child with alalia, facial expressions and gestures are widely used in communication.

A child with underdeveloped speech I level, due to correction:

- understanding and distinguishing the terms of surrounding objects and actions with them from speaking;
 - to tell the different parts of the body and the names of the clothes;
 - determination of the most common actions, some physiological and sensory-affective states;
 - expressing their wishes using simple requests and requests;
 - to answer simple questions with one-word or two-word phrases without using hints; in some cases, the use of sound sets is allowed.
- you spoke at the II level of underdevelopment:
- connecting objects with their quality and functional purpose;
 - oral explanations of familiar objects are familiar;
 - comparison of known objects according to their individual, most clearly visible properties;
- understanding of different grammatical categories singular and plural nouns, imperative and indicative moods of verbs, agreement of island, merit, barys, win and east, and some simple prepositions;

- phonetically correct spelling of early genesis sounds, vowel sounds of the first line;
- twos and threes used in prepositions reflect the rhythmic-intonational structure of idioms and can be repeated by themselves;

- to communicate with the help of phrases and simple, less exaggerated sentences.

Speech underdevelopment at level III:

- oral comprehension according to the parameters of the age norm;
- phonetically correct formation of the spoken voice;
- to be able to correctly describe the content of idioms used in their own speech;
- to have the experience of using simple, general, and complex sentences in their own speech, combining them, and telling a story;
- to acquire the basic skills of repeating a story;
- to have dialogical speaking skills;
- to acquire the skills of word formation: formation of terms from the verb to the figurative, from the noun and the verb, from the noun to the diminutive and augmentative forms, etc.;
- in independent speech, behavior is grammatically correct according to the size of the language. All cases and numbers must be clearly indicated;
- simple and all complex prepositions - are used in sufficient quantities;
- words of various lexical and grammatical groups (nouns, verbs, conjunctions, adverbs, adjectives, etc.)

At stage IV of speech development:

- creating stories and narratives;
- have the opportunity to create history with your own talent;
- sufficient use of simple and complex phrases in independent speech, complicating them with adverbs of cause and effect, general parts of a sentence, etc., - understanding and use of simple and complex phrases in independent speech;
- understand all lexical and grammatical categories of words and retain them in speech
- acquisition of word formation skills of all parts of speech, transfer of these skills to other lexical material;
- formation of colloquial speech according to the phonetic parameters of the Karakalpak language;
- teaching the correct sound-syllable formation of speech.

Alalia is a very complex speech disorder. Its complexity stems not only from the multiplicity, diversity, and interaction of language disorders, but also from the ambiguous relationships between nonlinguistic and language disorders.

There is reason to consider alalia a language disorder, which is characterized by deformation of the structural and functional side of the language and is not in a cause-and-effect relationship with disorders of non-linguistic forms of mental activity. In accordance with this understanding of alalia, it is advisable to direct speech therapy work with children mainly to the formation in them of the patterns of functioning of the language mechanism.

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